

1 Title:

2 Suicide vulnerability due to increased suicide-related Tweets: A case-only analysis

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14 Running title

15 Suicide vulnerability due to Tweets

16

17 Keywords

18 public health, twitter, social media, suicide

19

20 **Abstract**

21 **Background:** As social media has recently become more widespread, its impact on
22 health cannot be ignored. Although prior research has examined links between mass
23 media and suicide, little research exists regarding relationships between social media and
24 suicide. The goal of the present study was to identify factors underlying individuals'
25 vulnerability to suicide based on recent increases in suicide-related tweets.

26 **Methods:** A case-only study was performed on persons who committed suicide during
27 the period from January 1, 2011, through December 31, 2014, having obtained suicide
28 death data from Japanese demographic statistics. Additionally, the daily number of
29 suicide-related tweets during that time was compiled from a commercial service. For each
30 personal characteristic, estimates of effect modifications were fit to a logistic regression
31 or multinomial regression model. Odds ratios (OR) or relative risk ratios (RRR) were
32 used along with 95% confidence intervals (CI). For a sensitivity analysis, unexpected
33 deaths other than suicide were also addressed.

34 **Results:** When the increase rate from the previous day of suicide-related tweets was at
35 or above the 95th percentile, for suicides occurring three days thereafter, and for
36 individuals aged 40 years or younger, there was significantly high effect modifications
37 (OR=1.09, 95% CI 1.03-1.15 compared with older individuals). Additionally, males
38 (OR=1.12, 95% CI 1.07-1.18), those who were unemployed (RRR=1.12, 95% CI 1.02-
39 1.22), those who were divorced (RRR=1.11, 95% CI 1.03-1.19), and residents of urban
40 areas (OR=1.26, 95% CI 1.17-1.35) had significantly high effect modifications. For
41 unexpected deaths other than suicide, for deaths occurring seven days after a sudden
42 (extreme) increase in suicide-related tweets, and after the death of a spouse, significant
43 effect modifications were observed (RRR=1.08, 95% CI 1.02-1.15). No significant effect

44 modifications were revealed for any other personal characteristic.

45 **Discussion:** The present study revealed modifications based on personal characteristics
46 that associated suicide-related tweets to suicidal death. Results also indicated that for
47 unexpected deaths other than suicide, there were practically no effect modifications. In
48 other words, effect modifications appear to be specific to suicide. A possible interpretation
49 of these results is that an extreme increase in suicide-related information on social media
50 may modify suicide death risk.

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64 **Introduction**

65 The Internet and social media has recently been an important source of health-
66 related information (Norman, 2011; Lau et al., 2012). Furthermore, the importance of
67 suicide prevention has also been indicated. Suicide prevention among young people, who
68 spend a significant amount of time on the Internet and social media, is a related
69 concern(World Health Organization, 2014), leading to several recent suicide prevention
70 studies (Woolf, Bantjes & Kagee, 2015; Ross, Kőlves & De Leo, 2016).

71 Recent evidence suggests that reporting suicide through mass-media has
72 influenced trends in completed suicides. Indeed, several researchers are concurrently
73 studying the effect of conventional mass media on mental health (Corrigan et al., 2005;
74 Dietrich et al., 2006; Song et al., 2016), as well as the occurrence of copycat suicides
75 resulting from mass-media reporting (Sisask & Värnik, 2012; Yang et al., 2013; Suh,
76 Chang & Kim, 2015; Jang et al., 2016). To avoid the increased suicide risk caused by
77 mass-media reports, WHO has issued recommendations for media coverage of suicides
78 (World Health Organization, 2008).

79 In this regard, information on social media could play an important role in the
80 dissemination of appropriate information regarding suicides (Jashinsky et al., 2014; Sueki,
81 2015; Perry et al., 2016; Rice et al., 2016). Here, investigating the effects of social media
82 on suicide is an important public health issue. Nevertheless, little is known regarding the
83 relationship between social media and suicide risk.

84 The goal of the present study was to identify factors underlying vulnerability to
85 suicide resulting from sharp increases in suicide-related posts on Twitter. Twitter data is
86 relatively easy to manipulate, whereby tweets can be used as a surrogate marker for
87 information diffusion within popular social media platforms. To accomplish this, a case-

88 only analysis was conducted, as detailed below.

89

90 **Method**

91 **Study design**

92 Case-only designs, originally used to examine gene-environment interactions,
93 were recently proposed by Armstrong (2003) for the identification of effect modifiers due
94 to time-varying exposures ((Armstrong, 2003). The present study used data from suicides
95 only to calculate case-only odds ratios (ORs), enabling identification of personal
96 characteristics that made an individual more susceptible to suicide due to a numerical
97 increase in suicide-related tweets. A Poisson time-series (shown in the following formula)
98 provides the background for this method:

99

$$100 \log(E(Y_t)) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \textit{tweet} + \beta_2 \textit{characteristic} + \beta_3 \textit{tweet} \times \textit{characteristic}$$
$$101 \quad \quad \quad + \textit{confounders}$$

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103 With a case-only design, since completed suicides provide the only data points,
104 it is not possible to estimate β_0 , β_1 , β_2 , or β_3 . Instead, I estimated β_3 using a logistic
105 regression. This method is detailed in other documents (Armstrong, 2003; Gatto et al.,
106 2004; Schwartz, 2005). In the present study, however, where three or more categories of
107 personal characteristics were used, a multinomial regression was conducted to estimate
108 the relative risk ratio (RRR). The RRR of category X, vis-a-vis contrast categories, is
109 expressed in the following formula (Beckett Theodore Anagnoson et al., 1993):

110

111
$$RRR = \frac{Pr(y = \textit{category } X)}{Pr(y = \textit{reference category})} = e^{X\beta(\textit{category } X)}$$

112

113 With this approach, I estimated the interactions between increases in suicide-
114 related tweets and personal characteristics; in other words, this included the estimation of
115 the effect modification on suicides based on increased suicide-related tweets.

116

117 **Data Collection**

118 **Mortality data**

119 Mortality data was obtained from Japanese demographic statistics, published by
120 the Japanese Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare, for the period from January 1, 2011,
121 to December 31, 2014. Obtained data included sex, date of death, address code of the
122 deceased, marital status of the deceased, main occupation of the deceased, cause of death
123 based on the International Classification of Disease (ICD) 10 code, and age at death. Data
124 obtained for cause of death was within the ICD 10 code W00-Y59 range. Although X60-
125 X84 is noted as “suicide,” the main outcome of the present study, for a sensitivity analysis,
126 other external causes of death and unexpected death were also obtained (W00-X59、 Y01-
127 Y59). The following personal characteristics were used as potential modifiers: age at
128 death, sex, main occupation of the deceased, marital status of the deceased, and residential
129 area type (city area/rural area).

130 **Twitter data**

131 Total tweets were extracted from between January 1, 2011, and December 31,
132 2014. Search conditions were as follows: (1) tweets including any of the Japanese words
133 for “suicide” or “self-death.” (2) In addition to (1), tweets containing “prevention,”

134 “avoidance,” “countermeasure,” “support,” “project,” “symposium,” “conference,”
135 “panel discussion,” or “discussion.” The number of tweets found with (2) was subtracted
136 from the number of tweets found with (1), and results were defined as "suicide-related
137 tweets," with the number of tweets calculated daily.

138 In addition to general tweets, Twitter has a “retweet” function used for the
139 purpose of sharing information, as well as “reply” and “mention” functions, including the
140 user’s name. All of these tweets were also extracted. Tweet numbers are impacted by
141 external noise (changes in Twitter user numbers, problems with the Twitter system, etc.).
142 Thus, I reduced noise using a method proposed by Sano et al. (Sano & Takayasu, 2010).
143 For the noise-eliminated tweet numbers, calculation was made for the increase-decrease
144 ratio from the previous day. When the increase-decrease ratio from the previous day was
145 at or above the 95th percentile, this was defined as "exposure to suicide-related tweet
146 (+)"; when this ratio was less than the 95th percentile, this was defined as "exposure to
147 suicide-related tweet (-)."

148

149 **Data analyses**

150 Dividing suicide deaths from unexpected deaths, calculations were made, for
151 each personal attribute, number of deaths, and percentages. Age, mean values, and
152 standard deviations were calculated for descriptive statistics. For the main analyses,
153 suicide death was the main dependent variable. Age was binarized into age 40 or
154 younger—as this was the age group assumed to be most exposed to Twitter—and age 41
155 and older. Since age, sex, and residence area were two-category variables, logistic
156 regressions were used to calculate case-only ORs. Since main occupation and marital
157 status had three or more categories, multinomial regression was used to calculate case-

158 only RRRs.

159 With potential modifiers as the dependent variable, analyses were performed
160 with the independent variable being whether or not the individual was exposed to a
161 suicide-related tweet three days and seven days before the date of death. Logistic
162 regressions (when the dependent variable was a binary variable) or multinomial
163 regressions (when the dependent variable was a variable with three or more categories)
164 were performed, and 95% confidence intervals (CI) of the respective case-only ORs or
165 case-only RRRs were calculated. Since no analogous study using social media exists, I
166 used meteorological conditions as a reference to determine the number of lag days
167 necessary for the current study. In research concerning deaths due to meteorological
168 conditions (Schwartz, 2005), case-only ORs have been estimated with an effect period
169 set at two days. Since Twitter effects are not as biologically direct as meteorological
170 conditions, with the hypothesis of a longer lag than for meteorological events, the present
171 study used Lag 3 and Lag 7 days. Also, since personal characteristics and suicide-related
172 tweets are not related, covariates were not used (Gatto et al., 2004). Excluded from the
173 analyses were any subjects with missing values for age or occupation, or when the marital
174 status was "Other."

175 For the sensitivity analysis, unexpected deaths other than suicide were the
176 dependent variable, with the same analyses performed as for the main analyses. All
177 analyses were conducted using the statistical software package Stata 14.2 (StataCorp LP,
178 College Station, TX, USA). A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

179

180 **Ethical issues**

181 The protocol for this study was reviewed and approved by the Okayama University

182 Graduate School of Medicine, Dentistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Okayama
183 University Hospital, Ethics Committee (First approval No. 914, Change approval (change
184 of research period) No. 1013).

185

186 **Results**

187 Table 1 shows personal characteristics for the subjects. There were 159,490
188 persons with suicide deaths. Of these, 35,374 (22.2%) were age 40 and younger, and
189 103,893 were male (65.1%). There were 115,072 with unexpected deaths other than
190 suicide. Of these, 6,177 (5.4%) were age 40 and younger, and 63,594 were male (55.3%).

191 Table 2 presents case-only ORs and RRRs for each potential modifier calculated
192 in the main and sensitivity analyses. In the main analyses of suicide deaths, significant
193 effect modifications were observed for all personal characteristics (age, sex, main
194 occupation, marital status, and area of residence at time of death). When the increase rate
195 from the previous day of suicide-related tweets was at or above the 95th percentile, for
196 suicides occurring three days thereafter, individuals aged 40 years or younger had
197 significantly high effect modifications (OR=1.09, 95% CI 1.03-1.15 compared with older
198 people). Additionally, males (OR=1.12, 95% CI 1.07-1.18), unemployed (RRR=1.12,
199 95% CI 1.02-1.22), those who were divorced (RRR=1.11, 95% CI 1.03-1.19), and
200 residents of urban areas (OR=1.26, 95% CI 1.17-1.35) had significantly high effect
201 modifications. Those who were widowed had a significantly smaller effect modification
202 when compared to those who were married (RRR=0.83, 95% CI 0.77-0.89). With the
203 exception of unemployment for the occupation attribute, significant relationships were
204 also observed for the 7-day lag.

205 For the sensitivity analyses of unexpected deaths other than suicide, with the

206 exception of marital status, there were no significant effect modifications for any of the
207 personal characteristics. As for marital status, widowers had a significantly larger effect
208 modification than those who were married (7-day lag: RRR=1.08, 95% CI 1.02-1.15).
209 However, for the 3-day lag, there were no significant relationships for any of the personal
210 characteristics.

211

212 **Discussion**

213 Using a large-scale data set, the present study revealed that personal characteristics
214 modified due to the effect of suicide-related tweets included sex, main employment at the
215 time of death, marital status, and residence area at the time of death. This study also
216 observed the converse, namely that there were nearly no effect modifications for
217 unexpected deaths other than suicide. Thus, the present results appear to be specific to
218 suicide. The present study used tweets as a surrogate marker for social media use, and the
219 findings can be interpreted as indicating a change in risk due to an extreme increase in
220 suicide-related information being disseminated through social media as a whole.

221 The present results showed that persons aged 40 or younger were more
222 susceptible to suicide due to an increase in suicide-related tweets. This age group accounts
223 for the largest proportion of Twitter's daily users(I&SBBDO, 2014). Thus, these
224 individuals are more likely to be exposed to this suicide-related information. Furthermore,
225 females tended to be at a lower risk for suicide than males in relation to increases in
226 suicide-related tweets. It has been reported that, in Japan, compared with male suicides,
227 females engage in more self-injurious behaviors prior to an attempted or completed
228 suicide (Kodaka et al., 2016). Thus, females who complete suicide are likely more
229 impacted by factors other than suicide-related tweets when compared to males.

230 As for main occupation at the time of death, unemployment indicated a higher
231 risk modification than self-employment. Surveys of attempted suicides in Japan(The
232 Japan Foundation, 2016) have observed that a large percentage of persons who attempt
233 suicide are unemployed. Furthermore, those who are unemployed may have more
234 opportunities to use social media than those who may have workplace-related restrictions.
235 Thus, unemployed individuals may be more susceptible to the effects of an extreme
236 increase in suicide-related tweets.

237 As for marital status, widows had a lower risk than those who were married,
238 while the risk for divorcees was highly modified. This is thought to reflect age-related
239 effects, inasmuch as, compared with married persons, a greater number of widowers are
240 aged 41 or older, with a larger number of divorcees aged 41 or younger. Although the
241 percentage of married persons aged 41 or older was 89.79%, the same relative percentages
242 were 99.5% for widows and 82.29% for divorcees.

243 Compared with rural residents, urban residents had a higher risk modification.
244 Although Internet usage in Japan is rising, users are still highly concentrated in urban
245 areas (Japanese Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, 2014). Thus, more
246 opportunities to use Twitter in urban areas likely leads to a higher risk modification for
247 urban residents.

248 A characteristic of Twitter in Japan is its use as a lifeline. For example, when a
249 natural disaster occurs, people naturally seek help via Twitter, including a search for
250 psychological support (Umihara & Nishikitani, 2013; Pal, 2014; Jung & Moro, 2014;
251 Miura et al., 2015). Meanwhile, Twitter and other social media sites sometimes serve as
252 platforms for spreading false information(Takayasu et al., 2015). Thus, it has been
253 suggested that improving health literacy requires making accurate health information

254 more available through social media (Norman, 2011; Mesko, Gyórfy & Kollár, 2015;
255 Fredriksen, Harris & Moland, 2016; Mackert et al., 2016; James & Harville, 2016).
256 Against this backdrop, the present study's identification of personal characteristics that
257 make an individual more susceptible to the impact of an extreme increase in suicide-
258 related tweets is of significance in defining persons who require intervention, with the
259 aim of improving public health and welfare.

260 This is the first study to clarify the relationship between social media and suicide
261 death risk. Such findings could become an important knowledge base when considering
262 future suicide prevention measures. Inasmuch as official Japanese demographic statistics
263 were used, the data are highly valid. Also, since there was a 10% random sampling of
264 tweets, the data were generally collected in an unbiased way. Thus, the data had high
265 reliability, with a large sample size. At 35.0 million people, Japan has a high number of
266 active monthly Twitter users (The Huffington Post, 2016), with a high user percentage of
267 31% (Japanese Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, 2015); thus, Twitter
268 was a valid surrogate marker.

269 A few study limitations should be noted. First, I could not investigate data that was
270 unavailable from Japanese demographic statistics. Next, it is possible that the tweets were
271 not collected accurately. In other words, some tweets related to suicide may have been
272 missed. For example, messages using ASCII art or net slang could not be extracted.
273 Additionally, while it is thought that specific usage times could impact effect
274 modifications, no data exists regarding Internet/social media usage times. Finally, I did
275 not investigate correlations between mass-media reports and tweet numbers.

276

277 **Conclusion**

278 Using a case-only analysis, the present study identified personal characteristics
279 of increased risk for suicide based on an increase in suicide-related tweets. Results
280 showed that suicide risk increased for males, divorcees, unemployed individuals, urban
281 residents, and individuals over 40. It is necessary to minimize public health strains by
282 identifying people susceptible to the diffusion of suicide information on the Internet.

283

284 **Acknowledgments**

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286 regarding the Twitter data. Additionally, I obtained tremendous support from the
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289 provided editorial support.

290

291 **Competing Interests**

292 The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

293

294 **Author Contributions**

295 Toshinaru Mitsuhashi conceived and designed the study plan, collected and analyzed
296 the data, contributed the analysis software, wrote the paper, and prepared the figures and
297 tables.

298

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301

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